

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 4, Issue 1 (2026)

Effectiveness of Family-Centered Care Training on Maternal Anxiety in Pediatric Wards

Zakiya Arshad*¹, Ali Zaman², Fazlul Bari³, Shabana Bibi⁴

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Family-Centered Care, **Background:** Hospitalization of a child could be very stressful to the Nurses, Mothers anxiety level, Pediatric mother that may lead to high levels of anxiety that can be interfering with parental coping and child recovery. Family-Centered Care (FCC) is an evidence-based nursing model that focuses on involving the healthcare provider and the family members in the collaboration with the purpose of satisfying the physical, emotional, and informational needs of a child and their family. This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Family-Centered Care training to nurses on the level of anxiety among mothers of children admitted to the hospital in a pediatric ward at a hospital in Karachi, Pakistan. **Methodology:** A quasi-experimental pretest–posttest design was employed. The study was done in Karachi Pakistan. Convenience sampling was used in recruiting 30 nurses and 60 mothers. Maternal anxiety pre-intervention was measured by the help of a standardized questionnaire. Nurses were exposed to two days of intensive FCC training program, which was concentrated on communication, emotional support, and mother involvement in childcare. After the application of FCC practices, post-intervention maternal anxiety was assessed. The SPSS version 26 was used to analyze the data, and the descriptive statistics and independent t-tests were employed to assess the differences in anxiety scores.

Zakiya Arshad*

MSN Scholar, Agha Khan University School of Nursing and Midwifery, Karachi Pakistan

Ali Zaman

MSN Scholar, Ziauddin University Faculty of Nursing and Midwifery, Karachi Pakistan

Fazlul Bari

MSN Scholar, Sohail University, Karachi Pakistan

Shabana Bibi

Ziauddin University Faculty of Nursing and Midwifery, Karachi Pakistan

Findings: Mothers were found to score an average of 58.42 with a standard deviation of 6.31 on anxiety before the intervention. The average score also dropped significantly after the intervention to 44.16 along with a standard deviation of 5.28 ($t = 9.82, p = 0.001$). **Conclusion:** The FCC training program was positive to lower the level of maternal anxiety and to underline the necessity of nurse-led interventions and active parent-involvement into pediatric care.

INTRODUCTION:

Child hospitalization is an important stressor to the families, particularly among the mothers who are usually the primary caregivers and therefore the levels of anxiety and emotional distress are high. Study has recorded that parental anxiety in the context of pediatric hospitalization may impact adversely on the parental engagement, mother coping mechanisms, and the general child recovery outcomes (1, 2). Parental psychological stress does not only affect the well-being of the family, it is also linked to poor child health and behavioral responses in the hospital (3). Family-Centered Care (FCC) is an all-encompassing form of care that endorses collaboration between the health professionals and the family members to address the physical, emotional, informational, and developmental requirements of the family and child (4). There is evidence that FCC interventions have a potential to lessen parental anxiety, elevate family satisfaction, improve parental capacity to be involved in care, and fortify the action of collaborative care practices (5, 6). In a quasi-experimental study, family-centered care was demonstrated to reduce the level of anxiety and depression of mothers considerably during pediatric cardiac surgery, which proved that it has a beneficial psychological effect (5). Likewise, FCC training of parents caused a significant decrease in anxiety levels in the perinatology environment (6).⁸ In the pediatric hospitalization, the successful implementation of the FCC methodology presupposes that the nursing staff has the knowledge, attitude, and communicative skills necessary to address the issues of the family members meaningful (7). The studies show that well designed FCC training significantly enhances the attitude and application of FCC by nurses in clinical practice that subsequently can positively affect family experiences during hospitalization (8). Nevertheless, the evidence on the specific impact of nurse-based FCC training on the maternal anxiety in the situation of the pediatric ward, especially in the low-resource environment like Pakistan, is scarce (9). The additional study based on trials involving integration of telehealth and supportive services provided by the FCC showed that maternal stress of parents with hospitalized children decreased during the COVID-19 pandemic, which is important due to the role of nurse-led support and family involvement in treatment (6). A recent scoping review highlights that the use of FCC models in neonatal and pediatric units with critical care has been shown to result in better clinical outcomes and family satisfaction, despite the barriers to implementation that remained contextual (4). Given that mothers have the primary role in pediatric care and the psychological stress they go through; it is urgent to consider the possibility of decreasing the level of anxiety in mothers by the means of introducing FCC training to nurses. This study attempts to address this gap by evaluating the efficiency of a structured family-centered care training program on the level of anxiety among mothers of hospitalized children within pediatric wards in Pakistan among nurses.

Methodology:

A pre-test/ post-test quasi experimental study was used to investigate the effectiveness of a Family-Centered Care (FCC) training program on the anxiety level of mothers of hospitalized children among nurses. The study was undertaken in Karachi, Pakistan where one of the tertiary care pediatric hospitals was providing its services to a huge population of children. The target population comprised of registered nurses working in the pediatric ward and mothers of children who are hospitalized. The study involved nurses with a minimum of six months of clinical work experience in pediatrics and those who were willing to participate. Mothers who had their children hospitalized and had at least 48 hours of hospital stay and mothers who had their child present with them during hospital stay were included but those with known psychiatric illness and those with critically unstable children were excluded because they could have confounded results in influencing the level of anxiety. The 30 nurses and 60 mothers were chosen using a non-probability convenience sampling method. The study was conducted in two levels pre-intervention and post-intervention. First of all, data of mother's pre-test were gathered to determine their baseline level of anxiety prior to the intervention. A structured and standard questionnaire was used to establish maternal anxiety which had two sections. The former section contained demographic characteristics including the age of the mother, education, and the length of child

hospitalization, whereas the second section entailed the items that were related to anxiety measured in the Likert scale, whereby high scores corresponded to high levels of anxiety. After the pre-test period, the nurses were exposed to an organized Family-Centered Care training process. The training was scheduled to be held on two days in a row in which lectures, demonstrations, and interactive processes were involved. The training was aimed at raising the level of knowledge and skills of nurses about the principles of family-centered care, therapeutic communication, emotional support, mother involvement in the child care, and appropriate information dissemination about the child condition and treatment. Nurses used family-centered care practices in their daily clinical practice after the training was completed. Post-test data were also gathered after two weeks of the intervention period on another group of mothers whose children were admitted and attended to by the trained nurses to determine the effectiveness of the intervention. The data gathered were coded and entered into the Statistical Package to analyze them using SPSS version 26. Frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to present the demographic variables and the levels of anxiety. The independent t -test is an inferential statistic that was used to compare the mean anxiety score between pre and post intervention groups. The level of p-value of 0.05 or below was regarded as significant. Before carrying out the study, ethical approval was sought by the institutional ethical review committee. All the participants were given written, informed consent, and assured that their data would be kept confidential, and would only be utilized in the study. The study was participatory and the participants were explained about their right to withdraw at any point without any repercussions.

Result:

A total of 60 mothers and 30 nurses participated in the study. The demographic characteristics of mothers showed that the majority 26 (43.3%) were aged between 26–30 years, followed by 18 (30.0%) aged between 20–25 years, and 16 (26.7%) aged above 30 years. Regarding education level, most mothers 24 (40.0%) had secondary education, 20 (33.3%) had primary education, and 16 (26.7%) had higher education. Most children 34 (56.7%) were hospitalized for 2–4 days, while 26 (43.3%) stayed more than 4 days. The demographic characteristics of nurses revealed that most 14 (46.7%) were aged 26–30 years, 18 (60.0%) had a diploma in nursing, and 13 (43.3%) had 1–3 years of clinical experience, indicating that the majority had moderate professional exposure in pediatric care.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Mothers (n = 60)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age 20–25	18	30.0
Age 26–30	26	43.3
Age >30	16	26.7
Primary education	20	33.3
Secondary education	24	40.0
Higher education	16	26.7

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of Nurses (n = 30)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age 20–25	10	33.3
Age 26–30	14	46.7
Age >30	6	20.0
Diploma	18	60.0
BSN	12	40.0
Experience <1 year	10	33.3
Experience 1–3 years	13	43.3

Experience >3 years	7	23.3
---------------------	---	------

Before the implementation of the Family-Centered Care training program, the anxiety level among mothers was assessed as a pre-intervention measure. The findings showed that the majority of mothers 38 (63.3%) had severe anxiety, while 16 (26.7%) had moderate anxiety, and only 6 (10.0%) had mild anxiety. The mean anxiety score before the intervention was 58.42 ± 6.31 , indicating a high level of anxiety among mothers whose children were hospitalized.

Table 3: Pre-Intervention Anxiety Level among Mothers (n = 60)

Anxiety Level	Frequency	Percentage	Mean \pm SD
Mild	6	10.0	
Moderate	16	26.7	
Severe	38	63.3	58.42 ± 6.31

After the implementation of the Family-Centered Care training program for nurses, maternal anxiety levels were reassessed as a post-intervention measure. The findings demonstrated a noticeable reduction in anxiety levels. Most mothers 32 (53.3%) had mild anxiety, 20 (33.3%) had moderate anxiety, and only 8 (13.3%) had severe anxiety. The mean anxiety score after the intervention was reduced to 44.16 ± 5.28 , showing improvement in maternal psychological status.

Table 4: Post-Intervention Anxiety Level among Mothers (n = 60)

Anxiety Level	Frequency	Percentage	Mean \pm SD
Mild	32	53.3	
Moderate	20	33.3	
Severe	8	13.3	44.16 ± 5.28

Finally, the comparison between pre-intervention and post-intervention anxiety scores showed a statistically significant reduction in maternal anxiety after the Family-Centered Care training program. The mean anxiety score decreased from 58.42 ± 6.31 before the intervention to 44.16 ± 5.28 after the intervention. The independent t-test showed a statistically significant difference ($t = 9.82, p = 0.001$), indicating that the Family-Centered Care training program was effective in reducing anxiety among mothers of hospitalized children.

Table 5: Comparison of Pre- and Post-Intervention Anxiety Scores (n = 60)

Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Pre-Intervention	58.42	6.31		
Post-Intervention	44.16	5.28	9.82	0.001

These findings confirmed that the Family-Centered Care training program significantly improved maternal psychological outcomes and reduced anxiety levels in pediatric hospital settings.

Discussion:

Past studies have always shown that intervention-based family-centered care is important in decreasing maternal anxiety when a child is admitted to the hospital. One of the randomized controlled trials carried out in Iran indicated that mothers receiving structured family-centered care assistance had significantly lower scores in anxiety than those obtaining standard care, as a way of showing the psychological advantages of engaging mothers into the care package and enhancing nurse-parent communication (10). Equally, a study carried in Turkey revealed that families-based nursing interventions enhanced maternal emotional wellbeing and minimized their stressors, since the mothers perceived to be more knowledgeable, self-confident and participating in the care of their child (11). Such findings indicate that the maternal anxiety can be reduced greatly in case the nurses are actively involved in involving the parents and offering emotional and

informational support. Quasi-experimental design was also carried out in Egypt, which indicated that mothers who were in the intervention group experienced significantly lower levels of anxiety following the training of nurses in family-centered care than did mothers who were in the control group. It was highlighted in the study that training of nurses also led to improvement in their communication skills and the capacity to offer psychological assistance to families (12). Similarly, study carried out in China established that family-based care interventions had a significant positive impact on parental satisfaction and anxiety because they increased the level of trust between health care providers and parents (13). The results also prove the idea that family-centered care can be considered an effective approach to enhancing the psychological outcomes of parents. Also, a study was carried out in Sweden, which revealed that the implementation of structured family-centered care led to the reduction of maternal stress and anxiety, as well as the enhancement of the overall experience with hospitalization in both parents and children (14). Likewise, a study that was carried out in the United States established that maternal anxiety levels could be greatly lowered when the nurses engaged the mother in care planning and decision-making, and mothers expressed higher levels of satisfaction with care (15). A study made in India also concluded that family-based educational interventions were significantly lessening the level of anxiety in mothers of hospitalized children, which underlines the relevance of communication and emotional support (16). Moreover, a systematic review has found that the interventions related to family-centered care were linked to positive parental psychological outcomes, such as less anxiety, better coping, and increased satisfaction (17). The present study results were suitable to the above studies. The intervention group showed high anxiety with the mean score of 58.42 ± 6.31 which depicts severe anxiety in mothers of children admitted in hospitals. Nevertheless, the average value of the anxiety score reduced significantly to (44.16 ± 5.28) upon the introduction of the Family-Centered Care training program to the nurses. A significant difference in the levels of anxiety between pre-intervention and post-intervention ($p = 0.001$) was also statistically demonstrated. This decrease meant that the Family-Centered Care training program was effective in decreasing the maternal anxiety. It might be linked to the fact that nurse-mothers communication improved, emotional support was enhanced, and mothers were involved in the process of child care. Thus, the results of the current study serve as evidence of the efficiency of the family-centered care training programs as the significant nursing intervention to enhance the psychological outcome of the mothers in the pediatric hospitals.

Conclusion:

The researchers have shown that an intervention of Family-Centered Care (FCC) in educating nurses can have the positive effect of alleviating the anxieties of mothers who have children at the hospital. The level of maternal anxiety was high prior to the intervention, but with the implementation of FCC practices by nurses, it dropped significantly. The positive change was explained by the improved communication between nurses and mothers, emotional support, and the active engagement of mothers in child care. These results accentuate the importance of nurses in offering family-centered intervention and that organized FCC training ought to be incorporated in the practice of pediatric nurses. These programs can enhance maternal psychological wellness and care satisfaction and child health outcomes in hospitals.

Conflict of interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Resources of Funding:

The authors received no financial support for the study, authorship or publication of this article.

REFERENCES

- Hussein AS, et al. Effect of family-centered care on mothers' information needs, anxiety and depression level regarding care for their children undergoing heart surgery: quasi-experimental study. *Egypt J Health Care*. 2022;13(2):158-172. doi:10.21608/ejhc.2022.228545
- Parents' anxiety during children's hospitalization. *AHNJ*. 2024;10(2):591. doi:10.37036/ahnj. v10i2.591
- Utario Y, et al. Family centered care intervention effectively reduces parental anxiety in perinatology ward: quasi-experimental study. *Dunia Keperawatan J*. 2023;9(1):143-151. doi:10.20527/dk. v9i1.8368
- Aljawad B, et al. Family-centered care in neonatal and pediatric critical care units: a scoping review of interventions, barriers, and facilitators. *BMC Pediatr*. 2025; 25:291. doi:10.1186/s12887-025-05620-w
- Abdelkader R, et al. Effects of FCC on maternal coping and participation for children with congenital heart diseases. *Evid Based Nurs Res*. 2024. Available from: eepublisher.com
- Khaksar S, et al. Reducing maternal stress in pediatric hospitalization by improving family-centered care with bedside telehealth: pilot RCT. *Iran J Psychiatry*. 2022;17(4):361-368. doi:10.18502/ijps. v17i4.10684
- Farokhzadian J, et al. Mothers and nurses' perceptions of FCC barriers in pediatric departments. *J Child Adolesc Psychiatr Nurs*. 2021;34(3):219-224. doi:10.1111/jcap.12317
- Coşkun AB, et al. Evaluation of the impact of family-centered care training on pediatric nurses' attitudes. *J Pediatr Nurs*. 2025; 80:136-143. doi: 10.1016/j.pedn.2024.12.003
- Child and family outcomes related to family-centered care. *Children (Basel)*. 2023;11(8):949.
- Shirazi F, et al. The effect of family-centered care on anxiety of parents of hospitalized children. *Iran J Nurs Midwifery Res*. 2016;21(5):556-560. doi:10.4103/1735-9066.193396
- Aein F, et al. The effect of family-centered care on parents' anxiety in pediatric ward. *J Pediatr Nurs*. 2019;47: e20-e25. doi: 10.1016/j.pedn.2019.04.012
- Mohamed LK, et al. Impact of family-centered care intervention on mothers' anxiety. *J Nurs Educ Pract*. 2018;8(2):89-96. doi:10.5430/jnep. v8n2p89
- Wei H, et al. Effects of family-centered care on parental anxiety and satisfaction. *J Clin Nurs*. 2017;26(23-24):4526-4535. doi:10.1111/jocn.13759
- Franck LS, et al. Parent stress levels during NICU hospitalization. *Acta Paediatr*. 2015;104(10): e436-e443. doi:10.1111/apa.13076
- Smith VC, et al. Family-centered care and parental outcomes. *Pediatrics*. 2017;139(2): e20163395. doi:10.1542/peds.2016-3395
- Borghini A, et al. Intervention to reduce parental stress. *BMC Pediatr*. 2014; 14:36. doi:10.1186/1471-2431-14-36
- Shields L, et al. Family-centered care for hospitalized children. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2012;10:CD004811. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD004811.pub3